

Republic of the Philippines
City of _____
S.S.

SWORN AFFIDAVIT OF DECLARATION

I, _____, of legal age, Filipino, [single/married], and resident of _____, Philippines, after having been duly sworn in accordance with the law, do hereby promised to do the following if elected as Mayor of _____ City:

The first ordinance that I will sign as City Mayor is the ordinance **ADOPTING** the Freedom of Information Ordinance in Pasig City with the title:

“AN ORDINANCE STRENGTHENING THE OPERATIONALIZATION OF FREEDOM OF INFORMATION AND PROVIDING FOR A MECHANISM FOR THE DISCLOSURE OF PUBLIC RECORDS IN PASIG CITY, AND PROVIDING PENALTIES FOR THE VIOLATION THEREOF.” (*Ordinance Number 37; Series of 2018; 12 pages*)

By adopting this ordinance, I commit to ensuring its full implementation and enforcement in accordance with its provisions.

I understand that transparency and accountability in governance are vital for the trust and welfare of the people, and I commit to upholding these principles through the enforcement of this ordinance.

In the first year of my term, I shall also prioritize the following ordinances:

1. Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance
2. Anti-Epal Ordinance
3. _____

As a commitment to my pledge, I **shall resign** as City Mayor if I fail to sign the above ordinances within the first year of my term.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, I have hereunto affixed my signature this ___ day of April, 2025 at _____.

Affiant

SUBSCRIBED AND SWORN to before me this ___ day of April 2025, at _____ Affiant exhibited to me his/her valid government-issued ID with the following details:

ID Type: _____

ID Number: _____

Doc. No.: _____

Page No.: _____

Book No.: _____

Series of **2025**